

Config Replacement in Snakemake

Snakemake Hackathon 2025 - Report

1 Adding `--replace-workflow-config` to Snakemake to Fully Override Workflow Configuration

1.1 Author

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1.2 Associated Project Workitem

- [link to the issue](#)
- [link to the pull request](#)

1.3 Description

This work was completed as part of the Snakemake Hackathon.

Previously, when a configuration file was specified via the Snakemake CLI (e.g., `snakemake --config config.yaml`), the contents of that file were *merged* with any configuration variables already defined within the Snakefile. This meant that the CLI config would only extend or update existing values, rather than completely replacing the workflow's default configuration.

For example, if a Snakefile defined both `config["param1"] = "default_value_1"` and `config["param2"] = "default_value_2"`, and the CLI config specified `param1 = "cli_value"`, the resulting value of `config["param1"]` would be `"cli_value"`. However, `param2` kept its original value `"default_value_2"` from the Snakefile definition, instead of becoming undefined. This behavior could lead to unexpected results or conflicts when users intended to completely override the workflow's configuration with their CLI-provided settings.

1.4 Solution

This work item introduces the `--replace-workflow-config` parameter to the Snakemake CLI. When specified (e.g., `snakemake --replace-workflow-config config.yaml`), this parameter instructs Snakemake to *completely replace* the workflow's configuration dictionary with the contents of the provided config file. Any configuration variables defined in the Snakefile are effectively ignored.

1.5 Impact & Use Cases

This new functionality is particularly useful in scenarios where users want to run the same workflow with drastically different configurations without modifying the Snakefile itself. It simplifies configuration management and allows for greater flexibility in customizing workflows on the command line. Examples include running parameter sweeps or testing different data sources.

1.6 Testing

The new `--replace-workflow-config` parameter was tested with a comprehensive set of test cases, including:

- Workflows with and without pre-defined configuration variables.
- Config files with overlapping and non-overlapping parameters.
- Testing the interaction with other CLI options.
- Ensuring that the parameter does not introduce any regressions in the existing configuration merging behavior.